

BINO VA INSHOOTLAR XAKIDA UMUMIY TUSHUNCHA

Siddiqova Madinabonu

SamDAQU magistranti.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12681468>

Kirish. Kurilish amaliyotida ikki tushuncha, ya'ni "bino" xamda "inshoot" tushunchasi mavjud.

Jamiyatning moddiy xamda ma'naviy extiyojlarini kondirish uchun kishilar tomonidan bunyod etilgan kurilmalar inshoot deyiladi. Kishilarning biror faoliyatiga muljallangan va moslashtirilgan, ikki fazoga - bushlikka ega bulgan yer usti inshootlari bino deb ataladi.

Amaliy ish faoliyatida foydalaniladigan; binolarga alokasi bulmagan inshootlar injenerlik inshootlari deb ataladi. Bunday inshootlar (tugonlar, kupriklar, televizion minora, tunnellar, metro tuxtash joylari, dudburonlar, suv va don maxsulotlari saklanadigan katta idishlar va x.) fakat texnik vaziflarni bajarishga muljallangan buladi.

Binolar vazifasiga kura grujdan (turar-joy va jamoatchilik), sanoat va kishlok xujaligi binolari guruglariga ajratiladi. Grajdan binolariga kishilarning maishiy va jamoatchilik extiyojlariga muljallangan binolar kiradi. Bular turar-joy binolari (yashash uchun kurilgan uylar; yotokxonalar, mexmonxonalar va boshkalar) va jamoatchilik binolari (ma'muriy, ukuv, madaniy okartuv, savdo, kommunal xujalik, sport va boshka binolar) deyiladi.

Biror sanoat maxsulotini ishlab chikarishda mexnat jarayonini amalga oshirish uchun muljallangan va ichiga ishlab chikarish kurorlari joylashtirilgan binolar sanoat binolari deb ataladi (ustaxonalar, garajlar, elektrostansiyalar, omborlar, sex binolari), Kishlok xujaligi axtiyojlarini kondirish uchun foydalaniladigan binolar kishlok xujaligi binolari deb ataladi (molxona, parrandaxona, teplisalar, kishlok xujaligi maxsulotlari saklanadigan omborlar).

Yuqorida keltirilgan binolar tashki kurinishi va me'moriy-konstruktiv yechimlari bilan bir-biridan fark kiladi.

Binolarning ichki bushligini aloxida xonalarga ajratish mumkin (turar-joy xonasi, oshxona, sinflar, xizmat xonasi, sex va x.). Bir xil balandlik darajasida joylashgan xonalar kvavatlarni tashkil kiladi.

Uz navbatida kavatlararo yopmalar binoni balandligi buyicha kavatlariga ajratib turadi.

Xar kandy binoni bir-biri bilan boglik bulgan kism va elementlarga, ya'ni bir-birini tuldirib turuvchi va aniklab beruvchi uchta guruxga ajratish mumkin:

-xajmiy rejalashtirish elementlari, ya'ni bino xajmining yirik kislmlari (kavat, aloxida xonalar va x.);

-konstruktiv elementlar, ya'ni bino tuzilishini aniklab beruvchi kismlar (poydevorlar, devorlar, kavatlararo yopmalar, tom va x.);

-kurilish buyumlari, ya'ni konstruktiv elementni tashkil etuvchi nisbatan kichik kismlar (gisht, beton, oyna, pulat armatura va x.).

Xar kanday bino kuyidagi asosiy talablarga javob berishi kerak:

- vazifasiga muvofikligi, ya'ni bino kaysi jarayonga (maksadga) muljallangan bulsa, u shu jarayon talabiga tulik javob berishi kerak (yashash uchun kulay, dam olishga moslashtirilgan, mexnat kilishga kulay va x.);

- texnik tomondan muvofikligi, ya'ni bino kishilarni tashki ta'sirlardan (past yoki yukori temperatura, yogingar chilik, shamol va b.) tula asrashi, mustaxkam va ustivor bulishi, ekspluatasiya sifatlarini uzok yil davomida saklashi lozim;

- bino kurinishi me'morchilik va badiylik talablariga mos xolda tanlanishi, uning tashki (ekstyer) va ichki (interyer) kurinishi chiroyli, shinam, atrof-muxit bilan uygunlashgan bulishi kerak;

- iktisodiy jixatdan kulayligi, ya'ni bino va inshoot kurilishida mexnat sarfini kamaytirish, kurilish materiallari xamda vakti tejash kuzda tutiladi.

Binolar vazifasiga muvofikligiga kura ikki guruxga: asosiy va yordamchi vazifalarga muljallangan binolarga bulinadi. Masalan, maktab binosining asosiy vazifasi ukituvchilarni ukitishga muljallangan, shuning uchun xam bu bino asosan ukitish xonalaridan (ukuv sinfi, laboratoriyalar va x.) iborat bulishi kerak. Ammo bu binoda yordamchi vazifaga muljallangan xonalar ya'ni ovkatlanish xonasi ommaviy tadbirlar uchun muljallangan xonalar, maktab ukituvchilari va boshliklari xonalari xam mavjud bulishi kerak.

Binoda asosiy va yordamchi vazifaga muljallangan xonalarni bir-biri bilan tutashtiruvchi, kishilar xarakatini ta'minlaydigan joylar xam buladi. Bu joylar kommunikasiya xonalari deb ataladi. Bularga koridorlar (yulaklar), zinalar, daxlizlar va x. kiradi.

Binodagi xonalarning xammasida muljallangan vazifani bajarish uchun optimal shart-sharoit ya'ni muxit yaratilgan bulishi kerak. Muxit deganda juda kup omillar, ya'ni xonalarning shinamligi, asbob-uskunalarning kullay joylashganligi, xavo muxiti xolati (temperatura va namlik, xonadagi xavo almashinishi); tovush rejimi (eshitishni ta'minlash va shovkindan ximoya kilish); yoruglik rejimi; kishilarni evakuasiya kilish chogida xarakat kulayligi va xavfsizligini ta'minlash kabilar tushuniladi. Binoni loyixalashda bularning xammasini e'tiborga olish lozim.

Bu talablar binolarning xar bir turi va uning xonalari uchun "Kurilish meyerlari va koidalari" (KMK) asosida amalga oshiriladi. Binoning texnik muvofikligini butun binoga yoki

uning ayrim elementlariga ta'sir etayotgan xamma tashki kuchlar buyicha konstruksiyalarini xisoblash orkali aniklanadi. Bu ta'sirlar tashki kuch yoki muxit ta'siri kurinishida bulishi mumkin.

Tashki kuchlarga bino elementlari (kismlari)ning xususiy ogirligi (doimiy yuklar), uskunalar, kishilar, kor ogirligi, shamolning ta'sir kuchi (muvakkat yuklar), yer kimirlashi va uskunalarining tasodifiy buzilishi (avariyasi) natijasidagi ta'sirlar va b. kiradi.

Muxit ma'siriga esa temperaturaning ta'siri (konstruksiya chizikli ulchamlarining uzgarishiga olib keladi), atmosfera va tuprok namligi ta'siri (konstruksiya materiali xususiyatlarining uzgarishiga olib keladi), xavo okimi yunalishining ta'siri (xona ichidagi mikro iklimning uzgarishiga olib keladi); kuyosh nuri energiyasining ta'siri (konstruksiya materiali fizik-texnik xususiyatlarining birikmalar ta'siri) konstruksiyalarning yemirilishiga va buzilishiga olib keladi), biologik ta'sir (mikroorganizmlar va kurs-kumurskalar konstruksiyani yemiradi), bino ichidagi yoki tashkarisidagi shovkin ta'siridan xonaning normal akustik rejimini buzilishi kiradi.

Yukorida keltirilgan ta'sirlarni xisobga olgan xolda binolar mustaxkamlik, ustivorlik va pishiklik (uzok vakt buzilmaslik) talablarini kondirishi kerak.

Bino mustaxkamligi deganda uning tashki kuchlar ta'siridan uzok vakt buzilmasdan xamda ortikcha deformasiyaga uchramasdan uz vazifasini bajarib turishi tushuniladi.

Binoni tashki ta'sirdan uz muvozanatini saklab turishi binoning ustivorligi (turgunligi) deb ataladi.

Kurilish me'morlari va koidalariga (KMK) kura binolar uzok vakt uz vazifasini ado etishi buyicha 1U darajaga bulinadi: 1 - xizmat davri 100 yildan ortik; P - xizmat davri 50 yildan 100 yilgacha; Sh - xizmat davri 20 yildan 50 yilgacha va, 1U - xizmat davri 5 yildan 20 yilgacha muljallangan binolar.

Binolarga kuyilgan asosiy texnik talablardan yana biri binoning yongin xavfsizligidir.

Kurilishda ishlatiladigan materiallar va konstruksiyalar yonish darajasiga karab yonmaydigan, kiyin yonadigan va yonuvchan guruxlarga bulinadi.

Bino konstruksiyalari olovbardoshlik chegarasi bilan xam xarakterlanadi. Bu binoning olov ta'sirida uz mustaxkamligini, ustivorligini saklab tura olishi uchun ketgan vakt bilan yassi konstruksiya elementlari uchun esa ularda teshik-yoriklar paydo bulishi yoki konstruksiyaning olovga teskari yuzasidagi temperatura 140°S gacha kutarilishi uchun ketgan vakt bilan belgilanadi.

Bino va konstruksiyalarni olovbardoshligi jixatdan besh darajaga bulish mumkin. Eng katta olovbardoshlik 1 darajali binolarga, eng kichik olovbardoshlik esa U darajali binolarga tegishli buladi.

Olov bardoshligi 1,P va Sh darajali binolar tosh material yoki pishik gishtdan kurilgan, 1U darajali binolar esa sirti suvalgan yogochli, U darajalisi suvalmagan yogochli binolar xisoblanadi. Olovbardoshdigi 1 va P darajali bulgan binolar devori, tayanchlari, ora yoamalari, ichki tusik devorlari (parda devor) yonmaydigan bulishi kerak. Olovbardoshligi Sh darajali binolarda devorlari va tayanchlari yonmaydigan, ora yopmalari va ichki tusik devorlari esa kiyin yonuvchi buladi, Yogoch binolar 1U va U darajali olovbardoshdikka ega bulib, yongin xavfsizligi talablariga kura ular ikki kavatdan baland bulmasligi kerak.

Bino loyixasini yaratishda iktisodiy talablar bilan bir katorda xonalarning katta-kichikligi va shakli jixozlari axolining talab va extiyojlariga mos kelishi xam e'tiborga olinishi kerak.

Texnik talablar masalarini xal kilishdagi iktisodiy muvofiklik binoning mustaxkamligi, ustivorligi va uzokka chidamligi ta'minlanishibilan bir katorda 1 m² maydon satxi yoki 1 m³ bino xajmining narxi belgilangan kiymat chegarasidan oshib ketmasligini nazarda tutadi.

Bino narxini tushirish, uni rasional rejalashtirish va yuza satxini, uy xajmin i xamda ichki va tashki pardoiz ishlarini belgilashda extiyojdan ortikcha sarflarga yul kuymaslik xisobiga, bino turi va ekspluatasiya sharoitini xisobga olib eng kulay va optimal konstruksiyalarni tanlash, bino kurilishida fan va texnika yutuklarini xisobga olib zamonaviy usullarni kullash orkali amalga oshiriladi.

Binolar xalk xujaligi axamiyatiga molikligiga va boshka ekspluatasion sifatlariga kuyiladigan talablarga binoan turt klassga bulinadi. 1 klass binolarga - yuksak talablarni kanoatlantiradigan, 1U klass binolari esa eng oz talablarni kondiradigan binolar kiritiladi. Binolar 1 klassli bulishi uchun 1 darajali utga chidamli va uzok vakt uz vazifasini utaydigan bulishi, shu bilan birga, a'lo navli materiallardan kurilgan konstruksiyalari yetarligidan ortikrok mustaxkam bulishi, xonalar kam xam xamda yukori sifatli pardoizlangan bulishi kerak. Yirik sanoat korxonalarining binolari, yukori ekspluatasion va me'morlik talablari kuyiladigan 9 kavatli va undan xam baland binolar 1 sinfga mansub xisoblanadi. Kichikrok korxonona binolari, balandligi 9 kavatgacha bulgan turar-joy va jamoat binolari P klassga kiradi. Urtacha ekspluatasion va me'moriy talablar kuyiladigan, balandligi 5 vakatdan oshmaydigan turar-joy binolari Sh klassga mansubdir. Eng kam ekspluatasion va me'moriy talablar kuyiladigan muvakkat (vaktinchilik) imoratlar esa 1U klassga kiritiladi. Binoning klassini loyixa tuzishni topshiradigan tashkilot bulgilaydi.

Devor materialiga kura binolar tosh devorli yoki yogoch devorli bulishi mumkin. Kurinishiga va katta-kichik ligiga kura esa mayda elementlardan (gisht, sopol blok, mayda blok) Kurilgan va yirik elementlardan (yirik bloklar, panellar, xajmiy blok va xokazolardan) kurilgan

binolar bulishi mumkin. Kavatlari soniga kura binolar kam kavatli (1-2 kavatli), urtacha kavatli (3-5 kavatli), kup kavatli (6-10 kavatli), juda baland (11-16 kavatli) va osmonupar (kavatlar soni 16 dan xam kup) binolarga bulinadi. Joylashishiga karab bino kavatlari yerdan yukorida, sokol kismida, yertula kismida (podval) joylashgan va monsarddan iborat bulishi mumkin.

Kurilish texnologiyasiga kura binolar: tayyor beton konstruksiyalardan yigilgan binolar, zavodda tayyorlangan industrial konstruksiyalardan montaj kilingan binolar, devorlari gisht, mayda blok va shu kabi mayda elementlardan tiklangan binolar - turkumiga bulinadi.

Keng tarkalganligiga kura binolar:

- andoza loyixa asosida kuriladigan ommaviy binolar (turar-joy binolari, maktablar, maktabgacha muassasalar, poliklinikalar, kino-teatrlar va b.);

- aloxida loyixalar asosida kuriladigan nodir binolar (teatrlar, muzeylar, sport binolari, ma'muriy binolar va x.) kabi turlarga bulinishi mumkin.

REFERENCES

1. Мурадов С. ПРОБЛЕМЫ ТУШЕНИЯ ПОЖАРОВ КЛАССА Е ЛИЧНЫМ СОСТАВОМ ПОЖАРНОЙ ОХРАНЫ В МИРЕ //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 758-773.
2. Rayimkulov A., Murodov S. Some Issues of Safety in the Use of Tower Cranes Used in Construction Projects //JournalNX. – С. 301-308.
3. Dildora X., Sirojiddin M. O 'zbekiston respublikasi hududida seysmoaktiv hududlar va zilzilaning xavfliligi //Innovative Development in Educational Activities. – 2024. – С. 167-172.
4. ЎҒЛИ Р. Х. Ф., СИРОЖИДДИН М. ИЗУЧЕНИЯ УСЛОВИЯ ТРУДА В КОМПАНИИ ЕВРОПЫ. МУРАДОВ СИРОЖИДДИН //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 10.
5. O'G'LI M. S. H. ANALYSIS OF "MEASURES TO ENSURE OCCUPATIONAL SAFETY IN THE FIELD OF CARGO TRANSPORTATION AND LOADING." //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 9.
6. Sirojiddin M., Umurzoq E. INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT OF WORKING CONDITIONS AND ENVIRONMENT THROUGH THE KAIZEN METHOD //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 12. – С. 42-47.

7. Rakhimov O. D., Muradov S. H. Digitalization of Instructions on Labor Protection and Safety Techniques //European journal of life safety and stability (EJLSS). – 2022. – Т. 24. – С. 80-86.
8. Muradov S. H. o ‘g ‘li, & Zayniyev, UU o ‘g ‘li.(2023). PRINCIPLES OF PASSING AND DOCUMENTING INSTRUCTIONS ON SAFETY TECHNIQUES //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – Т. 2. – №. 14. – С. 116-119.
9. Muradov S. ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF PROFITS IN THE FIELD OF LABOR PROTECTION //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 1239-1245.
10. МУРАДОВ С. ИЗУЧЕНИЯ ОХРАНА ТРУДЫ НА ПРОИЗВОДСТВЕ КОРЕИ //ХӨДӨЛМӨР, НИЙГМИЙН ХАРИЛЦАА СУДЛАЛ. – 2023. – С. 242-247.
11. СИРОЖИДДИН М. РАЖАБОВ ХУРШИД ФАХРИДДИН ЎҒЛИ. ИЗУЧЕНИЯ УСЛОВИЯ ТРУДА В КОМПАНИИ ЕВРОПЫ. МУРАДОВ СИРОЖИДДИН //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2023. – Т. 10. – С. 27.
12. Husan o ‘g ‘li M. S., Utkir o ‘g ‘li Z. U. PRINCIPLES OF PASSING AND DOCUMENTING INSTRUCTIONS ON SAFETY TECHNIQUES //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2023. – Т. 11.
13. Мурадов С. Определение отдыха и отпусков на основании нового трудового кодекса //Aholi bandligi sohasidagi davlat siyosatining amalga oshirishning dolzarb masalalari. – 2023. – Т. 10. – №. 26. – С. 17-21.
14. Muradov S. H. Safarov Sh. O ‘. MEHNAT SHAROITLARI VA MUHITINI “KAIZEN” USULI YORDAMIDA TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING INNOVATSION YECHIMLARI //PAXTA TOZALASH, TO ‘QIMACHILIK VA YENGIL SANOAT SOHALARINING TEXNOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH. – 2023. – С. 90-92.
15. Sirojiddin M. Mehanatni muhofaza qilishning tashkiliy-psixologik asoslaridagi mavjud muammolar //Ekologiya, aholi xavfsizligi va mehnat muhofazasining hozirgi kundagi dolzarb masalalari va istiqbollari. – 2023. – С. 133-137.
16. Sirojiddin M. Mehnat sharoitlari va muhitini “kaizen” usuli yordamida takomillashtirishning innovatsion yechimlari //Ekologiya, aholi xavfsizligi va mehnat muhofazasining hozirgi kundagi dolzarb masalalari va istiqbollari. – 2023. – С. 249-253.
17. Muradov S. H. o ‘g ‘li, & Egamov, DS o ‘g ‘li.(2023). INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS TO PROTECT WORKERS FROM DANGEROUS GAS AND TOXIC SUBSTANCES IN

- HAZARDOUS INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – T. 2. – №. 14. – C. 340-342.
18. Muradov S. ASSESSMENT OF THE CHEMICAL SITUATION IN AN ACCIDENT IN FACILITIES USING KTZM //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 1142-1152.
19. Sirojiddin M. Mehnatni muhofaza qilish sohasida yuk ortish va tushirish ishlaridagi yukchilar uchun ishlarning xavfsizligi kategori va qoidalari tahlili //Ekologiya, aholi xavfsizligi va mehnat muhofazasining hozirgi kundagi dolzarb masalalari va istiqbollari. – 2023. – C. 232-242.
20. Sirojiddin M. Mehnatni muhofaza qilishning rivojlanish tarixiy bosqichlarini o‘rganish //Ekologiya, aholi xavfsizligi va mehnat muhofazasining hozirgi kundagi dolzarb masalalari va istiqbollari. – 2023. – C. 243-248.
21. Sirojiddin M. Sanoat korxonalari rahbar va mutaxassislarining mehnat muhofazasi bo‘yicha bilimlarini tekshirishni raqamli texnologiyalar asosida tashkil etishning ahamiyati //Ekologiya, aholi xavfsizligi va mehnat muhofazasining hozirgi kundagi dolzarb masalalari va istiqbollari. – 2023. – C. 146-150.
22. Sirojiddin M. Xavfli sanoat korxonalarida ishchilarni xavfli gaz va zaxarli moddalar ta’siridan himoya qilishga qaratilgan inovatsion yechimlar //Ekologiya, aholi xavfsizligi va mehnat muhofazasining hozirgi kundagi dolzarb masalalari va istiqbollari. – 2023. – C. 402-405.
23. Muradov S. CONSTRUCTION-INSTALLATION ISHLARIDA KUTARAMA KRANLARDAN USE FUNDAMENTAL SECURITY OF SUPPLY //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 786-792.
24. СИРОЖИДДИН М. НЕКОТОРЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ ГРУЗОПОДЪЕМНЫХ КРАНОВ В СТРОИТЕЛЬНО-МОНТАЖНЫХ РАБОТАХ //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 167-177.
25. Raximov O. D. Muradov SH Sanoat korxonalari rahbari va mutaxassislarini mehnat muhofazasi bo‘yicha o‘qitish va bilimlarini sinovdan o‘tkazishni raqamlashtirish //INTELLEKT. MONOGRAFIYA. – 2023.
26. O‘G‘LI M. S. H. Mehnatni muhofaza qilishning rivojlanish tarixiy bosqichlarini o‘rganish //Aholi bandligi sohasidagi davlat siyosatining amalga oshirishning dolzarb masalalari. – 2023. – T. 10. – №. 26. – C. 8-16.

27. Muradov S. ENSURING SAFETY OF WORKERS IN CONSTRUCTION //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 493-501.
28. Muradov S. Ishlab chiqarishdagi avariyalarni o‘rganish va tahlil qilish //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 16. – С. 474-477.
29. СИРОЖИДДИН учитель-стажер М. Каршинский инженерноэкономический институт кафедра «Охрана труда и техника безопасности» Республики Узбекистан.(2024). НЕКОТОРЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ ГРУЗОПОДЪЕМНЫХ КРАНОВ В СТРОИТЕЛЬНО-МОНТАЖНЫХ РАБОТАХ. Zenodo //НЕКОТОРЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ.
30. Мурадов С. PRINCIPLES OF ENSURING THE SAFETY OF USING LIFTING CRANES IN CONSTRUCTION-ASSEMBLY WORKS //MODERN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 933-939.
31. Husan o‘g‘li M. S. Sanoat korxonalari rahbar va mutaxassislarining mehnat muhofazasi bo‘yicha bilimlarini tekshirishni raqamli texnologiyalar asosida tashkil etishning ahamiyati //Aholi bandligi sohasidagi davlat siyosatining amalga oshirishning dolzarb masalalari. – 2023. – Т. 10. – №. 26. – С. 180-183.
32. Muradov S., Xujaqulov A., Eshmuxamedov L. ORGANIZING TRAINING ON THE CAUSES OF EMERGENCY SITUATIONS, CHARACTERISTICS AND ACTION AT THE FOCUS OF INJURY //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 247-264.
33. Muradov S., Usmonov H. MEHNATNI MUHOFAZA QILISHNING RIVOJLANISH TARIXIY BOSQICHLARINI O‘RGANISH //Interpretation and researches. – 2024.
34. Muradov S. CHEMICAL STATUS ASSESSMENT AND ANALYSIS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 455-463.
35. Muradov S. MAIN INDICATORS OF LABOR PROTECTION MEASURES EFFICIENCY //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 473-484.
36. Muradov S. STUDY AND ANALYSIS OF WORKING ACCIDENTS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 444-454.
37. Muradov S. INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT OF WORKING CONDITIONS AND ENVIRONMENT THROUGH THE KAIZEN METHOD //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 485-492.
38. Sirojiddin M. KTZM QO ‘LLANILADIGAN OBYEKTlardagi AVARIYADA KIMYOVIY HOLATNI BAHOLASH. – 2024.

39. O'G E. L. A. A. et al. PHYSIOLOGICAL AND HYGIENE BASIS OF HUMAN LABOR ACTIVITY //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 11.
40. Husan o'g'li M. S., Shavkat o'g'li E. D. INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS TO PROTECT WORKERS FROM DANGEROUS GAS AND TOXIC SUBSTANCES IN HAZARDOUS INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2023. – C. 11-17.
41. Muradov S. THE SIGNIFICANCE OF ORGANIZING THE EXAMINATION OF KNOWLEDGE OF LABOR PROTECTION OF MANAGERS AND SPECIALISTS OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES ON THE BASIS OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 805-817.
42. Muradov S. ANALYSIS OF JOB SAFETY CATEGORY AND RULES FOR LOADING AND UNLOADING WORKERS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 788-804.
43. Muradov S. DEFINITION OF REST AND LEAVES BASED ON THE NEW LABOR CODE //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 774-787.
44. Muradov S. EMERGENCY EPIDEMIOLOGICAL, EPIZOOTIC AND EPIPHYTOTIC SITUATIONS. PARTICULARLY DANGEROUS INFECTIONS THAT CAUSE RARE DISEASES SUCH AS PLAGUE AND YELLOW FEVER //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 703-728.
45. Sirojiddin M. MEHNAT MUHOFAZASI SOHASIDAGI MAQSABLARNING IQTISODIY TAHLILI. – 2024.
46. Muradov S. EPISOTOTIC SITUATIONS, THEIR PREVENTION //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 831-851.
47. Muradov S. CAUSES, CHARACTERISTICS AND ACTIONS OF THE POPULATION IN THE FOCUSES OF DAMAGE OF EMERGENCIES OF A MAN-GENIC CHARACTER //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 729-744.
48. Рахимова Д. О. ОСНОВНЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ РЕЧЕВОГО ЭТИКЕТА У МЛАДШИХ ШКОЛЬНИКОВ //Интернаука. – 2017. – Т. 10. – №. 14 Часть 1. – С. 61.
49. Рузиева З. М., Рахимова Д. О. Воспитание творческой личности на основе изучения литературы в общеобразовательной школе //Современное образование (Узбекистан). – 2017. – №. 5. – С. 63-68.

50. Каипова Ж. М. АРНАЙЫ ПЕДАГОГТАРДЫҢ КӘСІБИ ҚҰЗЫРЕТТІЛІГІН ҚАЛЫПТАСЫРУДА АКТ ҚОЛДАНУ ЖОЛДАРЫ //ГЛОБАЛЬНАЯ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИЯ 2021: ЦЕНТРАЛЬНАЯ АЗИЯ. – 2018.
51. Хусанова Д. Г. ЭРТА БОСҚИЧЛАРДА ИЖТИМОЙ ЕТИМЛИКНИ ОЛДИНИ ОЛИШ ЮЗАСИДАН МАЖМУАВИЙ ИШЛАР МАЗМУНИ //ГЛОБАЛЬНАЯ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИЯ 2021: ЦЕНТРАЛЬНАЯ АЗИЯ. – 2018.
52. Хусанова Д. Г. ЭРТА БОСҚИЧЛАРДА ИЖТИМОЙ ЕТИМЛИКНИ ОЛДИНИ ОЛИШ ЮЗАСИДАН МАЖМУАВИЙ ИШЛАР МАЗМУНИ //ГЛОБАЛЬНАЯ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИЯ 2021: ЦЕНТРАЛЬНАЯ АЗИЯ. – 2018
53. Rakhimova D. O., Shomurodov S. S. ON THE CRITERIA FOR ASSESSING THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION AND THE LECTURES IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM OF UZBEKISTAN //Global Science and Innovations: Central Asia (см. в книгах). – 2021. – Т. 8. – №. 1. – С. 58-62.
54. Рахимов О. Д., Рахимова Д. О. Форсайт исследование по прогнозированию развития цифровизации высшего образования Республики Узбекистан. – 2021.
55. Рахимов О. Д., Рахимова Д. О. Форсайт исследование по прогнозированию развития цифровизации высшего образования Республики Узбекистан. – 2021.
56. Khusenovich R. A. LAW AND PRINCIPLES OF ENERGY SAVING IN FUNDAMENTAL PHYSICS THEORIES //Academy. – 2021. – №. 5 (68). – С. 39-43.
57. Oktyabrovna R. D. BO ‘LAJAK MENEJERLARDA “FORSAYT KOMPETENTLIK” NI SHAKLLANTIRISH METODIKASI //Современное образование (Узбекистан). – 2022. – №. 3 (112). – С. 68-74.
58. Oktyabrovna R. D. TYPES AND FORMS OF ORGANIZING MANAGEMENT SCIENCE EDUCATION //European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 10. – №. 2.
59. Рахимова Д. О. БЎЛАЖАК МЕНЕЖЕРЛАР ТАЙЁРЛАШДА ФОРСАЙТ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯСИДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИШНИНГ ЗАРУРИЯТИ ВА АҲАМИЯТИ //RESEARCH AND EDUCATION. – 2022. – С. 338.
60. Шомуродов Ш. Ш. и др. МАСОФАВИЙ ТАЪЛИМДА ТАЛАБАЛАРДАМУСТАҚИЛ ИЖОДИЙ ФИКРЛАШ КОМПЕТЕНТЛИГИНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯСИ //ТА'ЛИМ VA RIVOJLANISH TANLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – С. 36-41.

61. Рахимова Д. О. ФОРСАЙТ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯСИНИНГ МОҲИЯТИ, МАЗМУНИ ВА ФОРСАЙТ УСЛУБЛАРИ ТАҲЛИЛИ //INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON LEARNING AND TEACHING. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 3. – С. 95-99.
62. Рахимова Д. О. “MENEJMENT” FANINI O’QITISHDA FORSAYT TEXNOLOGIYADAN FOYDALANISH METODIKASI: Raximova Dilrabo Oktyabrovna, Qarshi muhandislik iqtisodiyot instituti “Biznes va innovatsion menejment” kafedrası assistenti, mustaqil izlanuvchi //Образование и инновационные исследования международный научно-методический журнал. – 2022. – №. 4. – С. 154-158.
63. Oktyabrovna R. D. FORESIGHT COMPETENCE FORMATION MODEL FOR FUTURE MANAGERS //Berlin Studies Transnational Journal of Science and Humanities. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 1.5 Pedagogical sciences.
64. Rakhimov O. et al. Analysis of foresight competency development model components in future ecologists //E3S Web of Conferences. – EDP Sciences, 2023. – Т. 462. – С. 03049.
65. Oktyabrovna R. D. BO’LAJAK MENEJERLARDA FORSAYT KOMPETENTLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA “FORSAYT METODLARI” DAN FOYDALANISHNING ZARURIYATI //Proceedings of International Conference on Scientific Research in Natural and Social Sciences. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 4. – С. 146-155.
66. Рахимова Д. О., Ефименко О. В. Эффективность использования иммунотерапии в комплексном лечении острых внебольничных пневмоний у детей раннего возраста //Биология и интегративная медицина. – 2017. – №. 5. – С. 15-20.
67. Рахимов О. Д., Отакулов У. Х., Рахимова Д. О. Образовательный форсайт качества и результативности самостоятельного образования //Вестник науки и образования. – 2021. – №. 7-1 (110). – С. 69-72.
68. Rakhimov O. et al. Analysis of developmental education models in the ecological education system in Uzbekistan //E3S Web of Conferences. – EDP Sciences, 2023. – Т. 458. – С. 06020.
69. Турсунов И. Э., Рахимова Д. О. Развитие виртуального предпринимательства на основе цифровой экономики //Economics. – 2021. – №. 1 (48). – С. 14-18.
70. Rakhimov O. et al. Methodology for using foresight technology in training future ecologists in Uzbekistan //E3S Web of Conferences. – EDP Sciences, 2023. – Т. 462. – С. 03048.
71. Рахимов О. Д. и др. Неиспользуемые возможности: дистанционного образования в Узбекистане //Научный журнал. – 2021. – №. 3 (58). – С. 72-75.

72. Dustkabilovich R. O., Oktyabrovna R. D. Educational quality in the era of globalization //Проблемы науки. – 2021. – №. 1 (60). – С. 36-39
73. Рахимов О. Д., Рахимова Д. О. Форсайт исследование по прогнозированию развития цифровизации высшего образования Республики Узбекистан. – 2021.
74. Oktyabrovna R. D. FORESIGHT COMPETENCE FORMATION MODEL FOR FUTURE MANAGERS //Berlin Studies Transnational Journal of Science and Humanities. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 1.5 Pedagogical sciences.
75. Sultonova D. N., qizi Siddiqova M. A. COLOR SCHEME IN THE FORMATION OF THE ARTISTIC ENVIRONMENT OF THE INTERIOR OF MODERN EDUCATIONAL CENTERS //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 14. – С. 109-115.
76. Muradov S. et al. EMERGENCY EPIDEMIOLOGICAL, EPIZOOTIC AND EPIPHYTOTIC SITUATIONS. PARTICULARLY DANGEROUS INFECTIONS THAT CAUSE INFECTIOUS AND COMMON DISEASES //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 281-318.
77. Muradov S. et al. STANDARDS OF SAFETY REQUIREMENTS FOR PRESSURE CABINETS, APPARATUS AND GAS EQUIPMENT //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 159-180.
78. Husan ogli M. S., Hamidulla o'g'li X. X. Siddiqova Madinabonu Asatilla qizi.(2021). NEW INNOVATIVE ENGINEERING SOLUTIONS TO THE PROBLEMS OF SIGNALIZATION AND SECURITY SYSTEMS //European Journal of Life Safety and Stability (2660-9630). – Т. 2. – С. 28-30.
79. Muradov S. et al. STUDY OF THE HISTORICAL STAGES OF THE SCIENCE OF LABOR PROTECTION //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 350-365.
80. Muradov S. et al. CHECKING KNOWLEDGE OF LABOR PROTECTION //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 386-400.
81. Muradov S. et al. MOVEMENT OF CHICTONIC PLATES, ORIGIN OF EARTHQUAKES //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 401-415.
82. Muradov S. et al. MAIN CONTENT AND COMPONENT PARTS OF THE SCIENCE" SAFETY OF CONSTRUCTION OF BUILDINGS AND CONSTRUCTIONS" //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 335-349.

83. Muradov S. et al. ANALYSIS OF SECURITY CATEGORY AND RULES FOR CARRIERS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 366-385.
84. Muradov S. et al. ADMINISTRATIVE BUILDINGS AND THEIR REQUIREMENTS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 257-280.
85. Muradov S. et al. STABILITY CALCULATION OF LOAD LIFT VEHICLES //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 205-234.
86. Muradov S. et al. CONTENT AND ESSENCE OF THE LAW AND LEGAL DOCUMENTS ON THE PROTECTION OF THE POPULATION AND TERRITORIES FROM EMERGENCIES //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 168-204.
87. Muradov S. et al. CAUSES OF NATURAL EMERGENCIES //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 92-130.
88. Muradov S. et al. ANALYSIS OF SAFETY REQUIREMENTS OF EQUIPMENT WORKING UNDER HIGH PRESSURE //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 131-167.
89. Qizi S. M. A. et al. O 'QUV BINOLARI VA O 'QUV MARKAZLARINI RANG YECHIMINI RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR HAMDA SUN'IY INTELLEKT ORQALI LOYIHALASH //Raqamli iqtisodiyot (Цифровая экономика). – 2024. – №. 6. – С. 325-332.
90. Qizi S. M. A., Namazovna S. D. JAMOAT BINOLARI VA O 'QUV MARKAZLARI UCHUN TASVIRIY SAN'AT VA RANG YECHIMINI LOYIHALASHDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNING O 'RNI //Raqamli iqtisodiyot (Цифровая экономика). – 2024. – №. 6. – С. 333-340.
91. Muradov S. et al. NATURAL EMERGENCIES, INFECTIOUS DISEASES //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 416-441.
92. Мурадов С., Каримов Б., Сиддиқова М. ПРОБЛЕМЫ ТУШЕНИЯ ПОЖАРОВ КЛАССА //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 600-618.
93. Muradov S., Karimov B., Siddiqova M. FAVQULODDA VAZIYATLARNING VUJUDGA KELISHI SABABLARI, VA FAVQULODDA VAZIYATLARDA HARAKAT QILISHGA O 'RGATISHNI TASHKIL ETISH //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 554-573.

94. Muradov S., Karimov B., Siddiqova M. MEHNATNI MUHOFAZA QILISHDA YUK KO ‘TARISH VOSITALARINI MUSTAHKAMLIKKA HISOBLASH //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 5. – C. 636-655.
95. Muradov S., Karimov B., Siddiqova M. FAVQULODDA VAZIYATLAR VA ULARNING TURLARI, TABIIY TUSDAGI FAVQULODDA VAZIYATLAR //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 5. – C. 656-680.
96. Muradov S., Karimov B., Siddiqova M. ISHLAB CHIQRISHDA O ‘TA YUQORI BOSIM OSTIDA ISHLOVCHI USKUNLARNING XAVFSIZLIK TALABLARI TAXLILI TEXNIK ASOSLARI //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 5. – C. 681-703.
97. Muradov S., Siddiqova M., Karimov B. KIMYOVIY AVARIYA HOLATINI BAHOLASH VA TAXLIL QILISH //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 5.
98. Muradov S., Siddiqova M., Karimov B. LABOR PROTECTION MEASURES EFFICIENCY //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 5. – C. 774-793.
99. Muradov S., Siddiqova M., Karimov B. KUCHLI TA’SIR ETUVCHI ZAHARLI MODDALAR AVARIYALARIDA KIMYOVIY HOLATNI BAHOLASH //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 5.
100. Muradov S., Karimov B., Asatilla M. MAMURIY BINOLAR VA ULARNING TAVSIFLANISHI //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 5.
101. Мурадов С., Каримов Б., Сиддиқова М. ОТПУСКОВ НА ОСНОВАНИИ НОВОГО ТРУДОВОГО КОДЕКСА //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 5. – C. 619-635.
102. Muradov S., Siddiqova M., Karimov B. CONDITIONS AND ENVIRONMENT THROUGH THE KAIZEN METHOD //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 5. – C. 794-808.
103. Muradov S., Karimov B., Siddiqova M. QURILISH ASHYOLARINING MEXANIK XOSSALARI //NEW RENASSAINCE CONFERENCE. – 2024. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 144-164.
104. Muradov S., Karimov B., Siddiqova M. QURILISH ASHYOLARINING TUZILISHI VA TASNIFI //NEW RENASSAINCE CONFERENCE. – 2024. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 98-121.

105. Muradov S., Karimov B., Siddiqova M. QURILISH ASHYOLARI TARKIBINI ILMIY ASOSLASH USULLARI //NEW RENASSAINCE CONFERENCE. – 2024. – Т. 1. – №. 4. – С. 122-143.
106. Muradov S., Siddiqova M., Karimov B. STUDY AND ANALYSIS OF ACCIDENTS IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 16-31.
107. Muradov S., Siddiqova M., Karimov B. PARTICULARLY DANGEROUS INFECTIONS THAT CAUSE CONTAGIOUS AND COMMON DISEASES //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 32-64.
108. Muradov S., Karimov B., Siddiqova M. FAVQULODDA VAZIYATLARDA TIZIMIGA DOIR QONUNCHILIK //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 574-599.
109. Muradov S., Karimov B., Asatilla M. “BINO VA INSHOOTLARNI XAVFSIZLIGI” FANINING ASOSIY MAZMUNI //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 809-824.
110. Dustkabilovich R. O. et al. Modern lectures and methods of organizing problematic lectures //Проблемы науки. – 2020. – №. 2 (50). – С. 46-49.
111. Хужакулов А. Х. Значение инновационных технологий в организации самостоятельной работы студентов в системе высшего образования //Вестник науки. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 4 (61). – С. 113-117.
112. Рахимов О. Д. и др. Неиспользуемые возможности: дистанционного образования в Узбекистане //Научный журнал. – 2021. – №. 3 (58). – С. 72-75.
113. Rakhimov O. et al. Methodology for using foresight technology in training future ecologists in Uzbekistan //E3S Web of Conferences. – EDP Sciences, 2023. – Т. 462. – С. 03048.
114. Каримов С. М. и др. Нормативно-правовая база в области гражданской защиты в Республике Узбекистан //Теоретические и прикладные вопросы комплексной безопасности: Материалы. – 2019. – С. 36.
115. Rashidov N. S. et al. Stepped plow with cutting disc for tillage of sloping fields //IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science. – IOP Publishing, 2022. – Т. 1076. – №. 1. – С. 012023.
116. Хужакулов А. Х. У. Использование серы в сельском хозяйстве Узбекистана и обучение требованиям безопасности //Проблемы науки. – 2021. – №. 6 (65). – С. 96-102.

117. Berdimuratov P. et al. Seeder of exact seeding of seeds of cotton on the crest with drip irrigation //E3S Web of Conferences. – EDP Sciences, 2021. – Т. 264. – С. 04044.
118. Норбаев Э. К., Хужакулов А. Х. У. Доля затрат на эксплуатацию техники для подготовки кормов //Life Sciences and Agriculture. – 2020. – №. 4. – С. 21-24.
119. Muradov S., Xujaqulov A., Eshmuxamedov L. ORGANIZING TRAINING ON THE CAUSES OF EMERGENCY SITUATIONS, CHARACTERISTICS AND ACTION AT THE FOCUS OF INJURY //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 247-264.
120. Muradov S. et al. EMERGENCY EPIDEMIOLOGICAL, EPIZOOTIC AND EPIPHYTIC SITUATIONS. PARTICULARLY DANGEROUS INFECTIONS THAT CAUSE CONTAGIOUS AND COMMON DISEASES //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 52-89.
121. Muradov S. et al. STANDARDS OF SAFETY REQUIREMENTS FOR PRESSURE CABINETS, APPARATUS AND GAS EQUIPMENT //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 159-180.
122. Xakim o'g'li X. A. MUHANDISLIK YO 'NALISHI TALABALARING UMUMKASBIY TAYYORGARLIGIGA QO 'YILGAN TALABLAR //PROSPECTS AND MAIN TRENDS IN MODERN SCIENCE. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 6. – С. 60-63.
123. Muradov S. et al. NATURAL EMERGENCIES, INFECTIOUS DISEASES //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 416-441.
124. Muradov S. et al. MOVEMENT OF CHICTONIC PLATES, ORIGIN OF EARTHQUAKES //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 401-415.
125. Muradov S. et al. STUDY OF THE HISTORICAL STAGES OF THE SCIENCE OF LABOR PROTECTION //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 350-365.
126. Muradov S. et al. CHECKING KNOWLEDGE OF LABOR PROTECTION //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 386-400.
127. Muradov S. et al. MAIN CONTENT AND COMPONENT PARTS OF THE SCIENCE" SAFETY OF CONSTRUCTION OF BUILDINGS AND CONSTRUCTIONS" //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 335-349.
128. Muradov S. et al. ANALYSIS OF SECURITY CATEGORY AND RULES FOR CARRIERS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 366-385.

129. Muradov S. et al. ADMINISTRATIVE BUILDINGS AND THEIR REQUIREMENTS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 257-280.
130. Muradov S. et al. EMERGENCY EPIDEMIOLOGICAL, EPIZOOTIC AND EPIPHYTOTIC SITUATIONS. PARTICULARLY DANGEROUS INFECTIONS THAT CAUSE INFECTIOUS AND COMMON DISEASES //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 281-318.
131. XUJAQULOV A. QISHLOQ XO ‘JALIGI SOHASIDA BO ‘LAJAK MUTAXASSISLARNI KASB TANLASH VA KASBIY SHAKLLANISHINING PSIXOLOGIK MUAMMOLARI //News of UzMU journal. – 2024. – T. 1. – №. 1.3. 1. – C. 230-233.
132. Xujaqulov A. IXTISOSLIK FANLARINI O ‘QITISHDA TALABALARNING TEXNIK IJODKORLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA PEDAGOGIK SHART-SHAROITLAR //Interpretation and researches. – 2024.
133. Xakim o‘g‘li X. A. SANOAT KORXONALARIDAN CHIQUYOTGAN ZARARLI GAZLARNING SANOAT RAYONLARIDA YASHOVCHI AHOLINING SALOMATLIGIGA TA‘SIRI //IJODKOR O‘QITUVCHI. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 36. – C. 28-31.
134. Xakim o‘g‘li X. A. UMUMKASBIY FANLARNI O ‘QITISH ORQALI TALABALAR TOMONIDAN SHAKLLANADIGAN TADQIQOTCHILIK QOBILİYATLARI //INNOVATION IN THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM. – 2023. – T. 3. – №. 35. – C. 321-326.
135. Khujaqulov A. K. ANALYSIS OF RADIOACTIVE DAMAGE TO SURFACES AND INDIVIDUALS //Innovative Development in Educational Activities. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 18. – C. 145-149.
136. Шоназаров Ж. У., Хужакулов А. Х. ТВОРЧЕСКАЯ И ИННОВАЦИОННАЯ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТЬ БУДУЩЕГО ПРЕПОДАВАТЕЛЯ И СПОСОБЫ ДОСТИЖЕНИЯ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНЫХ НАВЫКОВ //Вестник науки. – 2020. – Т. 1. – №. 12. – С. 55-60.
137. Muradov S. et al. STABILITY CALCULATION OF LOAD LIFT VEHICLES //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 5. – C. 205-234.
138. Muradov S. et al. CONTENT AND ESSENCE OF THE LAW AND LEGAL DOCUMENTS ON THE PROTECTION OF THE POPULATION AND TERRITORIES

- FROM EMERGENCIES //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 168-204.
139. Muradov S. et al. ANALYSIS OF SAFETY REQUIREMENTS OF EQUIPMENT WORKING UNDER HIGH PRESSURE //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 131-167.
140. Otabek M. et al. Dynamics And Stability Of A Composite Feed Cylinder In The Feeding Area Of Rotor Spinning Machines //Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results. – 2023. – С. 1152-1157.
141. Рахимов О. Д., Тогаев Ж. Х., Хужакулов А. Х. У. Усовершенствованный кормонасос для фермерских хозяйств //Academy. – 2019. – №. 6 (45). – С. 25-27.
142. Рахимов, О. Д. "Тогаев ЖХ, Хужакулов АХ Усовершенствованный кормонасос для фермерских хозяйств." Москва. Журнал «Academy 6 (2019): 45.
143. Rakhimov O. D., Togaev Z. K., Khuzhakulov A. K. Improved feed pump for farms //Akademy. – 2019. – Т. 6. – №. 45. – С. 25-27.
144. Жураев М. Н. и др. Кластер тармоқлари учун автомобил транспортида ташиш жараёнларини бошқариш моделларини шакллантириш //O'zbekistonda fanlararo innovatsiyalar va ilmiy tadqiqotlar jurnali. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 19. – С. 1318-1323.
145. Namroyev O., Togaev J., Keldiyorov R. N. Installation for testing the ability of oil-oxidizing microorganisms //E3S Web of Conferences. – EDP Sciences, 2023. – Т. 417. – С. 02015.
146. Zhuraev M., Togaev J., Yusufkhonov Z. Management of consumers needs for volume of transportation, taking into account the probable nature //E3S Web of Conferences. – EDP Sciences, 2023. – Т. 401. – С. 01066.
147. Норбаев Э. Қ., Тогаев Ж. Х. ОЗИҚА УЧУН ТЕХНИКАЛАРДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИШДАГИ ҲАРАЖАТЛАР УЛУШИ //ББК 1 Е91. – 2019. – С. 131.
148. Тогаев Ж. Х., Жураев М. Н., Назарова В. Ҳ. АВТОМОБИЛ ТРАНСПОРТИДА ОЗИҚ-ОВҚАТ МАҲСУЛОТЛАРИНИ ТЕРМИНАЛ ТАШУВЛАР АСОСИДА ЕТҚАЗИБ БЕРИШНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ //O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 19. – С. 1143-1151.
149. Сарвирова Н. С., Саматов Г. А., Тогаев Ж. ИННОВАЦИОННОЕ РАЗВИТИЕ В АГРОЛОГИСТИКЕ //Актуальные проблемы экономики и управления на

- предприятиях машиностроения, нефтяной и газовой промышленности в условиях инновационно-ориентированной экономики. – 2020. – Т. 1. – С. 175-185.
150. Жураев М. Н., Тогаев Ж. Х. МЕТОДИКА ЭФФЕКТИВНОГО РАСПРЕДЕЛЕНИЯ ПРОВОЗНЫХ ВОЗМОЖНОСТЕЙ АВТОТРАНСПОРТНЫХ СРЕДСТВ НА РАДИАЛЬНЫЕ МАРШРУТЫ //Актуальные проблемы экономики и управления на предприятиях машиностроения, нефтяной и газовой промышленности в условиях инновационно-ориентированной экономики. – 2020. – Т. 1. – С. 116-124.
151. Тогаев Ж. PHYSIOLOGICAL AND HYGIENE BASIS OF HUMAN LABOR ACTIVITY //NRJ. – 2024. – Т. 1. – №. 4. – С. 96-103.
152. Tog'ayev J. MEHNAT MUHOFAZASI VA XAVFSIZLIK TEXNIKASI BO 'YICHA YO 'RIQNOMALARNI O 'TKAZISH METADOLOGIYASI //NRJ. – 2024. – Т. 1. – №. 4. – С. 104-110.